

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CLINICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PAIN SYNDROME IN PATIENTS WITH NEUROLOGICAL AND NEUROSURGICAL PROFILE

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Abstract

The article discusses the clinical and psychological characteristics of pain syndrome in patients with neurosurgical and neurological profiles. Groups of patients are compared with each other according to the parameters characterizing the pain syndrome.

Keywords: Pain syndrome, clinical and psychological characteristics, chronic pain, emotional and personal characteristics, neurological patients, neurosurgical patients.

Introduction. Chronic pain is the leading cause of disability in economically developed countries, the incidence of chronic pain syndromes continues to grow and has no tendency to decrease. Neurological pathology is one of the leading causes of chronic pain syndrome. Psychological features of experiencing pain syndrome in patients with neurological and neurosurgical profile are currently an urgent topic for consideration, since in the age of information technology, many neurogenic pains arise as a consequence of a sedentary sedentary lifestyle.

The purpose of the study: to determine the clinical and psychological characteristics of pain syndrome in patients with neurological and neurosurgical profiles for the development of a program of psychocorrection.

Hypothesis No. 1 of the study: clinical and psychological characteristics of pain syndrome in spinal patients of neurological and neurosurgical profiles will differ.

Hypothesis No. 2 of the study: it is possible to identify certain psychological characteristics of the emotional and personal sphere that affect the intensity of pain syndrome in spinal patients of neurological and neurosurgical profiles.

The object of the study: spinal patients with chronic pain syndrome undergoing treatment at St. Petersburg State Medical University. Pavlova at the neurological and neurosurgical departments.

Subject of research: clinical and psychological characteristics of pain syndrome in spinal patients of neurological and neurosurgical profiles.

Stages of the study. The study was conducted in 2021-2022 among patients of the neurological and neurosurgical departments of PSPbSMU. Pavlova. The total number of subjects was 49 people. The selection criterion for the sample was the presence of pain syndrome, pathology leading to surgical intervention.

To achieve the objectives of the study related to the comparison of two groups of patients, the entire sample was divided into two groups. The first group consists of patients with a neurological profile, the second, respectively, of a neurosurgical profile.

The group of neurosurgical patients is characterized by an age from 33 to 74 years (average age 52.93), among them 17 women, 10 men, with diagnoses such as M48.0 (spinal canal stenosis), M51.1 (degeneration

of intervertebral discs of the lumbar and other departments with radiculopathy), M42.1 (spinal osteochondrosis in adults). Localization mainly in the lumbar region (L3-L5 vertebrae), as well as in the cervical and thoracic regions.

The group of neurological patients consists of patients aged from 26 to 75 years (average age 53 years), among them 6 men, 16 women, with diagnoses such as I67.4 (hypertensive encephalopathy), M48.0 (spinal canal stenosis), M51.1 (degeneration of intervertebral discs of the lumbar and other departments with radiculopathy), G54.4 (Lesions of the lumbosacral roots, not classified elsewhere), M54.2 (Cervicalgia), M42.1 (osteochondrosis of the spine in adults). Localization of pain is mainly in the lumbar region (L3-L5 vertebrae), with a transition to the sacral region (S1), as well as in the cervical and thoracic regions (C5-C6, Th8-9).

The organization of the study took place in several stages. At the first stage, a hypothesis was formulated and methods and techniques, criteria for the inclusion of subjects in the study were selected.

At the second stage, the actual experimental psychological studies of the subjects were carried out. Studies with each patient were conducted within one day: the patient independently filled out part of the methods, and a clinical conversation was also conducted. The time spent on one patient was about 2 hours.

At the third stage, qualitative and quantitative analysis of the data obtained, interpretation of the results and formulation of the conclusions of the study were carried out.

Materials and methods. To achieve this goal, 45 patients (average age 34±12 years) with diagnoses were examined: Cerebral palsy, spinal stenosis, radiculopathy, disc herniation, with vertebral pain, with indications for surgery; and also – 22 patients (average age 30 ± 8 years) with vertebral pain, treated primarily, with the appointment of conservative treatment. Clinical and psychological and experimental psychological methods were used to assess emotional and personal characteristics (USF-1, Montgomery Scale, HADS, DN4, Pain-Detected, BPI, TOBOL, Big V, Lazarus coping Behavior questionnaire).

The calculation of mathematical and statistical data was carried out in the program STATISTICA v. 10

using the following methods of statistical analysis: descriptive statistics, comparative analysis using the Mann-Whitney criterion, Pearson correlation analysis.

Results.

1. Pain syndrome in neurological patients is characterized by moderate intensity; pronounced neuropathic component; increased level of anxiety and depression; low level of social frustration; leading strategies for overcoming chronic pain and coping strategies: "maintaining activity", "positive reassessment" and "self-control"; predominance of harmonic and ergopathic types of attitude to the disease.

2. Pain syndrome in neurosurgical patients is characterized by medium intensity; low level of anxiety and depression; increased level of social frustration; leading strategies for overcoming pain and coping strategies "keeping active", "decision planning" and "self-control"; predominance of sensitive and ergopathic types of attitude to the disease.

3. Neurosurgical patients experience and assess the level of pain lower than neurological patients. Neurosurgical patients are more frustrated than neurosurgical patients. Neurological patients have a more pronounced level of anxiety and depression, but are less prone to maladaptive mental reactions in the disease.

4. In neurological patients, the intensity of pain is associated with a strategy of taking responsibility, and in neurosurgical patients with depression and anxiety, pain management strategies "protection" and "exercise", there is also a feedback with extraversion. The neuropathic component of pain in patients of both groups is associated with the level of anxiety, in neurological patients also with a dysphoric type of attitude to the disease; in patients with a neurosurgical profile, there is a connection with depression, strategies for overcoming pain "search for support" and "protection", the level of social frustration, distancing, personal resources, willingness to consent, ergopathic type of attitude to the disease.

Conclusions. Within the framework of the study, various clinical and psychological characteristics of pain syndrome in neurological and neurosurgical patients were obtained; characteristics of the emotional sphere, coping strategies for overcoming pain syndrome are highlighted as targets for psychocorrection. The hypothesis put forward in this study - the clinical and psychological characteristics of pain syndrome in spinal patients of neurological and neurosurgical profiles will differ - has been proven.

The hypothesis put forward in this study - it is possible to identify certain psychological characteristics of the emotional and personal sphere that affect the intensity of pain syndrome in spinal patients of neurological and neurosurgical profiles - has been proven.

References:

1. Absi M.A., Rokke P.O. Can anxiety help us tolerate pain? // *Pain*. – 2017. – Vol. 46. – P.43–51.
2. Blumer D., Heilborn M. Chronic pain as a variant of depressive disease: the pain prone disorder // *Nerv. Ment. Dis.* – 2018. – Vol. 170. – P.381-406.
3. Fields H. Depression and pain: a neurobiological model // *Neuropsychol. Behav. Then* -2015. -Vol.4. -P.83-92.
4. Fishbain D.A., Goldberg M., Beagher B.R. Male and female chronic pain patients categorized by DSM –III psychiatric diagnostic criteria// *Pain*. -2015. – Vol.26. -P.181-197.
5. Keefe F. J. Cognitive-behavioral approaches to assessing pain and pain behavior. In: G. Gebhart, D. L. Hammond and T. S. Jensen (eds). *Proc of the VII World Congress of Pain*. N Y: Elsevier, – 1994. – Vol. 4. – P. 127-48.
6. Stoneham M.D., Cooper R., Quiney N.F. et al. Pain following craniotomy: a preliminary study comparing PCA morphine with intramuscular codeine phosphate. *Anesthesia*. – 1996. – Vol. 51. – P. 1176-8.